

METAL EVAPORATION IN WELDING

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Annotation. *In the given article fluid flow in both the welding arc and the weld pool will be described. The effect of weld pool fluid flow on the geometry of the resultant weld will be researched. Evaporation of alloying elements from the weld pool and its effect on the weld metal composition will be presented. Finally, the effect of active fluxes on weld penetration in GTAW will be described.*

Keywords. *Shielding gases, Gas–tungsten welding arc, buoyancy force.*

МЕТАЛЛИЧЕСКИЕ ИСПАРЕНИЯ В СВАРКЕ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье будет описано течение жидкости как в сварочной дуге, так и в сварочной ванне. Будет исследовано влияние течения жидкости в сварочной ванне на геометрию полученного сварного шва. Будет представлено испарение легирующих элементов из сварочной ванны и его влияние на состав металла шва. Наконец, будет описано влияние активных флюсов на проплавление сварного шва в GTAW.*

Ключевые слова. *Защитные газы, Газовая вольфрамовая сварочная дуга, выталкивающая сила.*

FLUID FLOW IN ARCS

Shows a gas–tungsten arc in GTAW with DC electrode negative. The shape of the electrode tip is characterized by the tip angle (also called included or vertex angle) and the extent to which the sharp point is removed, that is, the truncation.

Driving Force for Fluid Flow

The welding arc is an ionic gas, that is, a plasma, with an electric current passing through. The driving force for fluid flow in the arc is the **electromagnetic force or Lorentz force**. The buoyancy force is negligible. Mathematically, the Lorentz force $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$, where \mathbf{J} is the current density vector and \mathbf{B} is the magnetic flux vector. The current density vector \mathbf{J} is in the direction the electric current flows.

According to the right-hand rule for the magnetic field, if the thumb points in the direction of the current, the magnetic flux vector \mathbf{B} is in the direction that the fingers curl around the path of the current. Vectors \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{J} , and \mathbf{B} are perpendicular to each other.

According to the right-hand rule for the electromagnetic force, \mathbf{F} is in the direction out of and perpendicular to the palm if the thumb points in the direction of \mathbf{J} and the fingers stretch out and point in the direction of \mathbf{B} .

Effect of Electrode Tip Geometry

The welding arc is more or less bell shaped. The tip angle of a tungsten electrode in GTAW is known to have a significant effect on the shape of the arc—it tends to become more constricted as the electrode tip changes from sharp to blunt. The change in the shape of the electrode tip changes fluid flow in the arc plasma, which in turn changes the shape of the arc.

Figure 1. Gas–tungsten welding arc.

A. Sharp Electrode Consider the case of GTAW with DC electrode negative. The electric current converges from the larger workpiece to the smaller electrode tip. It tends to be perpendicular to the electrode tip surface and the workpiece surface, as illustrated in Figure 2.

The electric current induces a magnetic field, and its direction is out of the plane of the paper (as indicated by the front view of an arrow) on the left and into the paper (as indicated by the rear view of an arrow) on the right. The magnetic field and the converging electric current field together produce a downward and inward force \mathbf{F} to push the ionic gas along the conical surface of the electrode tip. The downward momentum is strong enough to cause the high-temperature ionic gas to impinge on the workpiece surface and turn outward along the workpiece surface, thus producing a bell-shaped arc, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Investigated the effect of the electrode tip geometry on heat and fluid flow in GTAW arcs. Figure 2 (left) shows the current density distribution in a 2-mm-long, 200-A arc produced by a 3.2-mm-diameter electrode with a 60° angle tip. The electric current near the electrode tip is essentially perpendicular to the surface.

The electromagnetic force, shown in Figure 2 (right), is downward and inward along the conical surface of the electrode tip. As shown in Figure 3, this force produces a high-velocity jet of more than 200m/s maximum velocity and the jet is deflected radially outward along the workpiece surface. This deflection of the high-temperature jet causes the isotherms to push outward along the workpiece surface, thus resulting in a bell-shaped arc.

Figure 2 Arc produced by a tungsten electrode with a sharp tip: (a) Lorentz force (**F**); (b) fluid flow.

B. Flat-End Electrode With a flat-end electrode, on the other hand, there is no longer an electrode tip to act as a fixed cathode spot, where the electric current enters the electrode. Consequently, the cathode spot moves around rather randomly and quickly in the flat electrode end. The time-averaged diameter of the area covered by the moving spot can be considered as the effective cathode spot size. Without a conical surface at the electrode end, the resultant Lorentz force is still inward and downward but the downward component is reduced, as illustrated. Consequently, the resultant arc can be expected to be more constricted.

Figure 3 Current density field (left) and Lorentz force field (right) in an arc produced by a tungsten electrode with a 60° tip angle.

The electromagnetic force, shown in Figure 3 (right), is downward and inward along the conical surface of the electrode tip. The driving forces for fluid flow in the weld pool include the buoyancy force, the Lorentz force, the shear stress induced by the surface tension gradient at the weld pool surface, and the shear stress acting on the pool surface by the arc plasma. The arc pressure is another force acting on the pool surface, but its effect on fluid flow is small, especially below 200 A , which is usually the case for GTAW.

Driving Forces for Fluid Flow

The driving forces for fluid flow in the weld pool include the buoyancy force, the Lorentz force, the shear stress induced by the surface tension gradient at the weld pool surface, and the shear stress acting on the pool surface by the arc plasma. The arc pressure is another force acting on the pool surface, but its effect on fluid flow is small, especially below 200 A (11, 12), which is usually the case for GTAW. The driving forces for fluid flow in the weld pool, shown in Figure 4.10, are explained next.

A. Buoyancy Force The density of the liquid metal (ρ) decreases with increasing temperature (T). Because the heat source is located above the center of the pool surface, the liquid metal is warmer at point a and cooler at point b . Point b is near the pool boundary, where the temperature is lowest at the melting point. Gravity causes the heavier liquid, induced Marangoni convection in a transparent pool of NaNO₃ with a defocused CO₂ laser beam. The NaNO₃ has a $\partial g/\partial T = -0.056 \text{ dyn/cm/}^\circ\text{C}$. Since its transmission range is from 0.35 to 3mm, NaNO₃ is opaque to CO₂ laser (10.6 mm wavelength) just like a metal weld pool is opaque to an arc. shows the flow pattern induced by a CO₂ laser beam of 2.5W power and 3.2mm diameter. The pool surface is just below the two arrows that indicate the directions of flow at the pool surface. The two counter rotating cells are, in fact, the two intersections between the donut-shaped flow pattern and the meridian plane of the pool. The outward surface flow is

much faster than the inward return flow, which is typical of Marangoni convection. As the beam diameter is reduced, convection grows stronger and penetrates deeper. It is worth noting that in conduction-mode (no-keyholing) laser beam welding, the pool surface can be concave due to Marangoni convection and surface tension and, in fact, this has been shown to be the case experimentally and by computer simulation. The concave NaNO_3 pool surface, however, is just a coincidence; the melt wets the container wall and the meniscus makes the pool surface concave. Additional $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$ to the NaNO_3 pool and reversed the direction of Marangoni convection. The $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$ is a surface active agent of NaNO_3 and, like S reduces the surface tension of liquid steel, it reduces the surface tension of NaNO_3 , $\partial\gamma / \partial C$ being $22\text{dyn}/(\text{cm}/\text{mol} \%)$. The NaNO_3 pool shown in Figure 4 contains 2mol % of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$ and its surface flow is inward. This flow reversion is because the surface tension is now higher at the center of the pool surface than at the pool edge. At the center of the pool surface, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$ is lower in concentration because it decomposes under the heating of the CO_2 laser beam. Blocks of solid NaNO_3 , both pure and with $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$, were welded with a defocused CO_2 laser beam. As shown in Figure 4, the weld in pure NaNO_3 is shallow and wide. This is because the thermal conductivity of NaNO_3 is low and heat transfer is dominated by the outward surface flow to the pool.

Figure 4 Marangoni convection with an inward surface flow in a NaNO_3 pool containing 2mol % $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOK}$ as a surface-active agent.

For the steel containing only 20 ppm sulfur, the outward surface flow carries heat from the heat source to the pool edge and results in a shallow and wide pool. For the steel containing 150 ppm sulfur, on the other hand, the inward surface flow turns downward to deliver heat to the pool bottom and results in a much deeper pool. In the small area near the centerline of the pool surface, the temperature is above 2000 K and the surface flow is outward because of negative $\partial\gamma / \partial T$. It is

worth noting that showed that based on a positive $\partial g / \partial T$ for liquid steel at all temperatures can overpredict the pool depth.

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